

e-ISSN: 3048-7927

Volume 09 Issue 01 Jan-
Apr 2026

*Corresponding Author:-
Kuldeep B Pawar,
Assistant Professor,
Department of Electrical
Engineering, Shree
Santkrupa Institute of
Engineering & Technology,
Ghogaon, Karad, MS,
India-415111

Submission Date: Nov 29,
2025

Copyright Received Date:
Dec 03, 2025

Enhancing Wind Energy Efficiency Using a Counter-Rotating Vertical Axis Turbine

**Kuldeep B Pawar^{1*}, Shubham M Shinde²,
Priyanka R. Shinde³, Aishwarya D. Apshinge⁴**

^{1,2,3,4}Assistant Professor, Department of Electrical
Engineering, Shree Santkrupa Institute of Engineering &
Technology, Ghogaon, Karad, MS, India-415111

ABSTRACT

With the rising global demand for electricity, conventional non-renewable energy sources are proving inadequate and contribute significantly to environmental pollution. As a result, renewable energy sources have gained prominence, with wind energy being one of the most viable alternatives. Wind turbines harness the kinetic energy of wind and convert it into electrical power. There are two primary types of wind turbines: horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWT) and vertical axis wind turbines (VAWT). While HAWTs require larger spaces and have lower efficiency, VAWTs are more compact and space-efficient. However, both types still suffer from efficiency limitations. This study focuses on enhancing the performance of a vertical axis wind turbine by introducing modifications to its generator. Unlike conventional designs where the stator remains stationary while the rotor rotates, this research explores a novel approach in which the stator is also set in motion. This counter-rotating mechanism aims to improve energy conversion efficiency and optimize electricity generation.

Keywords:- Counter-rotating wind turbine, vertical axis wind turbine (vawt), wind turbine performance optimization, kinetic energy utilization, generator modification.

INTRODUCTION

The global demand for electricity is rising rapidly due to industrialization, technological advancements, and expanding infrastructure. Conventional energy sources such as fossil fuels and coal, which have been the primary means of power generation, are not only limited in supply but also contribute significantly to environmental pollution. As these non-renewable resources continue to deplete, there is an urgent need to transition toward sustainable and renewable energy alternatives.

Renewable energy sources, including solar power, wind energy, hydroelectric power, geothermal energy, and biomass, offer a viable solution to meet the growing energy demand while minimizing environmental impact. These sources are sustainable, widely available, and do not contribute to air pollution or greenhouse gas emissions [1]. Among them, wind energy has emerged as one of the most promising solutions due to its efficiency and cost-effectiveness. Wind turbines play a crucial role in harnessing wind energy and converting it into electricity.

However, existing wind turbine designs face efficiency limitations [4]. Horizontal Axis Wind Turbines (HAWTs) require large land areas and are less effective in regions with fluctuating wind directions. Vertical Axis Wind Turbines (VAWTs), on the other hand, are more space-efficient and adaptable to variable wind conditions. Despite these advantages, further improvements are necessary to enhance their performance.

This study aims to improve the efficiency of vertical axis wind turbines by introducing modifications to the generator system. Unlike conventional designs where the stator remains stationary and the rotor rotates; this research explores a novel

approach by enabling counter-rotation of the stator. This innovative mechanism is expected to enhance energy conversion efficiency and optimize electricity generation, contributing to the advancement of sustainable power solutions [7].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Hossein Seifi Davari et al. (2024) Self-starting torque remains a major challenge for Darrieus Vertical Axis Wind Turbines (DVAWTs). This study optimizes air foil design, embossed blades (EBs), and blade height (H) to improve turbine efficiency. Using double-multiple stream tube theory (DMST) and particle swarm optimization (PSO), the NACA0015-Opt rotor demonstrated the highest power coefficient (C_p). Increasing H from 35 cm to 75 cm improved airflow, reduced drag, and significantly lowered self-starting torque. At H = 75 cm, the optimized EB-DVAWT reduced self-starting torque by up to 52.06% compared to the baseline smooth blade DVAWT. This study highlights the effectiveness of air foil and structural modifications in enhancing DVAWT performance.[10]

Ariyana Dwiputra Nugraha et al. (2025) The growing concerns over global warming and fossil fuel dependence have driven interest in vertical axis wind turbines (VAWTs) for renewable energy. This study introduces a rose flower-shaped turbine, which is additively manufactured and compared with existing Aero-leaf and Tulip turbines through numerical simulations at wind speeds of 3 m/s, 6 m/s, and 9 m/s. The Rose turbine demonstrated superior performance, generating 0.12 W at 3 m/s, 0.67 W at 6 m/s, and 2.34 W at 9 m/s, achieving the highest power coefficient ($C_p = 0.1$) at 3 m/s compared to the other models. The results were validated through experimental testing.

Additionally, Energy Payback Period analysis confirmed that the Rose turbine is an efficient solution for electricity generation in urban and rural areas.[7]

Paul Bayron et al. (2024) conducted an experimental study on the performance and wake effects of tandem wind turbines with co-rotating and counter-rotating rotor configurations. The study was carried out at a Reynolds number of 9.6×10^4 , analysing in-line turbine arrangements with different separation distances ranging from $1.25DT$ to $8DT$ and various tip-speed ratios. The results showed that the downstream turbine performed 20% better when rotating in the opposite direction to the upstream turbine at a separation distance of $1.25DT$. However, as the distance increased, the advantage of counter-rotation reduced. Wake velocity measurements indicated little effect on streamwise velocity but showed that turbulence levels were 33% higher in co-rotating arrangements. The study provides useful insights for improving wind turbine placement and efficiency in onshore and offshore wind farms [1].

Mohamed R. Shouman (2023), the performance of a counter-rotating Savonius wind turbine (CRSWT), a type of vertical axis wind turbine suited for low-wind conditions was enhanced through CFD simulations. Traditional experimentation for improving CRSWT efficiency is costly and complex, making numerical simulations a valuable alternative. The study introduced novel modifications, including curtain configurations and fin additions to the turbine blades, to improve efficiency. The curtain arrangements were designed to reduce opposing torque on each rotor, while fins directed wind flow to maximize blade efficiency. Simulation results showed that with optimal curtain lengths (500 mm, 550 mm) and angles (50° , 30°)

and a single fin addition, the CRSWT's power coefficient improved by nearly 48%. These findings suggest that selecting the right curtain arrangement and adding fins can significantly boost CRSWT performance [11].

M. Tariq Javaid et al. (2024) explored the potential of Twin Vertical Axis Wind Turbines (VAWTs) to enhance wind farm power density. Previous studies on twin-VAWTs primarily focused on parametric studies of isolated variables, which led to conflicting results due to the interdependence of variables. This research used a Taguchi orthogonal array (L16) combined with a modified superposition model to optimize power performance by considering design variables such as solidity ratio (σ), pitch angle (β), wind direction angle (δ), turbine spacing ratio (S/D), and rotational direction (ϕ). Unsteady CFD simulations were performed to evaluate power performance. The study ranked the design variables based on their impact on the optimum tip-speed ratio (TSR) and power coefficients, revealing a shift in optimal performance with TSR increases. The study showed that the optimum twin-VAWT configuration improved power efficiency by 23% at TSR 4.25, compared to the standalone VAWT. However, the orthogonal analysis method led to sub-optimal results, and a full factorial Design of Experiments (DoE) identified the best design, confirming the viability of twin-VAWTs for improving farm power density [4].

H.Y. Peng et al. (2024) investigated the aerodynamic performance of vertical axis wind turbines (VAWTs) in turbulent environments using 3D large eddy simulations (LES). The study aimed to understand how turbulence impacts VAWT aerodynamics under varying wind speeds, tip-speed ratios (TSRs), and

turbulence intensities. Validation with wind tunnel data from previous studies ensured the reliability of the results. The consistent discrete random flow generation (CDRFG) method was used to create turbulence in the incoming flow. The findings revealed that turbulence significantly influenced lift forces and dynamic stall onset but had minimal effects on drag. Power performance improvements were observed with increasing wind speed from 5 m/s to 10 m/s, with little further enhancement at higher speeds. These results provide valuable insights for optimizing VAWT design and operation in areas with fluctuating wind conditions and turbulence [8].

Omar S. Mohamed et al. (2023) explored the performance enhancement of twin Darrieus rotors, which are gaining attention for both wind and hydrokinetic applications. Previous studies suggested that the interaction between closely spaced rotors could improve efficiency, but the underlying physical mechanisms were not well understood. This study used unsteady Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) to analyse counter-rotating, two-blade Darrieus hydrokinetic turbines operating in both inward and outward rotation directions. The results indicated that the optimum center-to-center distance for the turbines is $2D$, and the optimal operating point shifted toward higher tip-speed ratios (TSRs). Efficiency improvements of 16.1% and 8.7% were observed for inward and outward twin rotor setups, respectively, compared to a standalone turbine. A detailed analysis of the local flow field revealed that the interaction between the rotors suppressed stream tube expansion, allowing more momentum flux into the rotor area. Additionally, changes in the inflow velocity direction increased the angle of attack, which in turn enhanced lift generation and improved efficiency [6].

Sadra Sahebzadeh et al. (2022) investigated the impact of rotor settings and relative arrangements on the power performance and aerodynamics of double-rotor vertical axis wind turbine (VAWT) arrays. Eight rotor settings were considered, including two relative rotational directions (co-rotating and counter-rotating), two relative positioning (downstream turbine positioned in leeward or windward of the upstream rotor), and two phase lags (0° and 180°). A total of 504 unique cases were analysed within rotor distance ($1.25d \leq R \leq 10d$) and rotor angle ($0^\circ \leq \Phi \leq 90^\circ$). Unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier–Stokes (URANS) CFD simulations, validated with experimental data, revealed that power performance was significantly influenced by rotor rotational direction and positioning, with up to an 8% variation in power coefficient (C_p).

The performance differences arose from the interaction between the upstream and downstream rotors' wakes and the shear layer created by their overlap. For windward-positioned arrays, co-rotation was preferred, while for leeward-positioned arrays, counter-rotation resulted in the highest C_p . Counter-rotating turbines with leeward positioning showed the highest efficiency, as the downstream rotor blade moved with the flow direction in the wake overlap region, minimizing energy dissipation and shear layer strength. Conversely, counter-rotating arrays with windward positioning exhibited the lowest C_p due to the downstream rotor moving against the flow, leading to increased velocity deficits and a stronger shear layer [9].

Yan Li et al. (2023) reviewed the use of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) technology in studying the aerodynamics of straight-bladed vertical axis wind turbines (SB-VAWTs), which are increasingly used in rural and marine

environments due to their simple shape, smart structure, and wind direction independence. Despite their advantages, improving the performance of SB-VAWTs remains challenging due to their complex aerodynamic characteristics. The study covers various aspects of CFD technology, including calculation domain size, meshing strategies, time step determination, and numerical solutions of the Navier-Stokes equations, turbulence model selection, and Y^+ value determination. The review also proposes solutions to 18 common issues encountered when applying CFD methods to SB-VAWT studies. This work provides valuable guidance for future research and simulations of SB-VAWTs using CFD technology [5].

M. Somoano et al. (2022) conducted an experimental study to assess the effect of trailing edge flexibility on the performance of a three-blade straight vertical axis wind turbine with a chord-to-diameter ratio of 0.16, operating at a moderately high Reynolds number ($Re_D = 4 \cdot 10^5$). The turbine blades, made from NACA-0015 profiles, were fixed with a pitch angle of 6° toe-out, and allowed for interchangeable trailing edges in the last 17% of their chord length. The study demonstrated that semi-flexible trailing edges could enhance the turbine's performance by extending the range of rotor operating regimes, leading to a 10% improvement in efficiency. However, excessive flexibility resulted in reduced efficiency. This research highlights the potential of trailing edge flexibility for improving the performance of vertical axis wind turbines [12].

Joachim Toftegaard Hansen et al. (2021) investigated the performance enhancement of pairs of vertical axis wind turbines (VAWTs) through two-dimensional CFD simulations. The study aimed to identify

turbine layouts that could increase the power output of VAWT farms. Over 11,500 hours of simulations were performed, considering factors such as wind direction, turbine spacing, and rotation direction. The simulations were conducted at a turbine diameter Reynolds number of 1.35×10^7 , with a mesh convergence study assessing the impact of mesh size, domain size, azimuth increment, number of iterations per time step, and domain cell density. The results revealed that pairs of VAWTs could achieve a 15% increase in power output compared to isolated turbines when spaced three turbine diameters downstream and positioned at a 60° angle to the wind direction. Additionally, when three turbines were placed in series, the power output increased by 3% compared to the pair configuration. This study provides valuable insights for optimizing turbine layouts to enhance farm power generation [3].

Wei-Hsin Chen et al. (2021) conducted a two-stage optimization study using computational fluid dynamics (CFD) to enhance the power output of multiple vertical-axis wind turbines (VAWTs) with straight blades. In the first stage, four configurations were evaluated and optimized using the Taguchi approach, considering three operational factors: the distance between the third turbine and the y-axis (H), the distance between the second and third turbines (B), and the placement of the fourth turbine. The results indicated that H had the most significant impact on performance, followed by B, with the placement of the fourth turbine having a lesser effect. In the second stage, optimization based on the Taguchi combination was refined by varying the B value. The optimal configuration, with $B = 6m$ and without the fourth turbine, increased the power output by approximately 3%, raising the

mean power coefficient (C_p) from 0.5026 to 0.5174. This enhancement was attributed to the Magnus effect from the first and second turbines. The study also showed that changing the rotation direction of the third turbine from counter clockwise to clockwise decreased the power output, reducing C_p to 0.3339. Overall, the optimized three-turbine system exhibited a 15.7% higher mean power coefficient ($C_p = 0.5174$) compared to a single VAWT ($C_p = 0.4473$) at a wind speed of 8 m/s and a tip-speed ratio of 2, highlighting the effectiveness of the optimized design in boosting power performance [2].

METHODOLOGY

The objective of this project is to develop an efficient and cost-effective wind turbine that utilizes recycled materials for sustainable energy generation. Approximately 70% of the turbine components are designed to be constructed using repurposed materials, making it an eco-friendly and economical alternative to commercial wind turbines. Several advancements have been incorporated to enhance its efficiency compared to conventional designs.

The design process began with selecting the most suitable wind turbine configuration either a Vertical Axis Wind Turbine (VAWT) or a Horizontal Axis Wind Turbine (HAWT) based on key performance parameters such as torque, tip-speed ratio (TSR), coefficient of power, and wind speed adaptability. After thorough research and comparison, it was determined that both types of turbines have distinct advantages and disadvantages. However, considering the operational wind speed range of 2.6 to 5.14 m/s, a VAWT was chosen as the optimal solution due to its ability to generate sufficient torque at low wind speeds.

One of the key advantages of VAWTs is their lower cut-in speed, which enables them to start operating within the required wind speed range. Additionally, VAWTs typically generate higher torque compared to HAWTs, making them better suited for directly driving the generator. Another important factor influencing this decision was the simplicity of the design. Unlike HAWTs, which require active yaw control to align with wind direction, VAWTs can capture wind from any direction without complex orientation mechanisms, making them more suitable for low-tech applications.

The next phase of the project involved selecting the most effective VAWT model. Two primary designs were considered:

1. **Darrieus Wind Turbine** – Known for its aerodynamic efficiency but requiring high start-up speeds.
2. **Savonius Wind Turbine** – Characterized by its simple construction and high torque output but lower overall efficiency.

To determine the best-suited model for this application, a comparative analysis was conducted, evaluating factors such as efficiency, torque generation, structural simplicity, and material requirements. The final design choice was made based on these considerations to ensure optimal performance and feasibility for real-world applications.

MODELLING AND ANALYSIS

The proposed system consists of several key components, each contributing to the functionality and efficiency of the counter-rotating vertical axis wind turbine. The design integrates carefully selected materials and electronic components to optimize power generation and structural stability. The following sections detail the construction and implementation of the system.

Blade Construction

The Savonius wind turbine blades are constructed using the following materials:

- **Metal Sheets:** Rectangular metal sheets measuring **45 cm × 25 cm** are utilized to form the blades, ensuring durability and efficient wind capture.
- **Plywood:** Two circular plywood pieces, each with a thickness of **3 mm**, are used to mount the blades securely.
- **Steel Rods:** These are employed to construct the shaft, which is directly connected to the generator to facilitate energy conversion.

Generator System

To improve efficiency, modifications have been introduced to the traditional generator design. Unlike conventional systems where the stator remains stationary, this design incorporates a counter-rotating stator to enhance energy output. The key components of the generator include:

- **Shaft:** A steel rod acts as the central shaft, supporting the turbine blades and transferring rotational energy. Bearings are incorporated to ensure smooth rotation.
- **Pulleys and Belts:** Two pulleys are installed a **larger pulley and a smaller pulley** maintaining a ratio of **3:1** to facilitate the movement of the stator and rotor.
- **Permanent Magnets:** **Neodymium magnets (NdFeB)** of **N35 grade** are used to generate a strong magnetic flux. These magnets, with a field strength of **1.21T**, are chosen due to their availability and effectiveness.
- **Copper Coil:** The winding is sourced from an old ceiling fan and modified for this application. The coil consists of **SWG 36 copper wire** with **350 turns**, ensuring optimal electromagnetic induction.
- **Brushes and Brush Holders:** Brushes from a repurposed mixer motor are used

to extract electrical output, while brush holders keep them in position.

- **Bearings: 6201-2RS bearings** (inner diameter: **12 mm**, outer diameter: **30 mm**) provide smooth rotational motion. These bearings, made from zinc alloy with a steel bush, are mounted on a metal frame for stability.

STRUCTURAL SUPPORT

A robust iron frame is designed to house the wind turbine, generator, and associated components. The frame is welded together, and holes are strategically drilled to accommodate bearings and fasteners. This structure ensures proper alignment and stability of the system during operation.

ELECTRONIC COMPONENTS

To monitor and regulate the system's performance, various electronic components are integrated:

- **Arduino Nano:** A microcontroller is used to process data and control system operations.
- **Hall Effect Sensor (A3144):** Detects the presence of magnetic fields, triggering changes in output voltage.
- **LCD Display (16×2):** Displays real-time operational data, including wind speed and power generation metrics.
- **LM2596 Buck Converter:** Functions as a voltage regulator, efficiently converting higher voltages to stable lower output voltages.
- **12V Battery:** A rechargeable battery stores the generated electricity, ensuring continuous power availability.

The integration of these components ensures efficient energy conversion and real-time monitoring, making the proposed wind turbine system both functional and reliable.

RESULT

The performance of the wind turbine was evaluated by measuring its rotational speed using a tachometer. The system incorporates pulleys with a 1:3 ratio, which effectively increases the rotational speed of both the rotor and stator by three times, enhancing the overall efficiency of power generation.

The output was analysed under two different operating conditions:

1. Conventional Mode: In this setup, only the **rotor rotates**, while the

stator remains stationary, following the standard generator configuration.

2. Counter-Rotating Mode: In this modified setup, both the **rotor and stator rotate in opposite directions**, creating a relative motion that enhances electromagnetic induction, potentially increasing power output.

Comparing these two approaches allowed for a comprehensive evaluation of the impact of counter-rotation on the efficiency and performance of the wind turbine.

RPM	Voltage (Conventional)	Voltage (Counter rotating)
30	7.56	15.12
40	10.08	20.16
50	12.6	25.2
60	15.12	30.24
70	17.64	35.28
80	20.16	40.32
90	22.68	45.26
120	30.24	60.48

RPM	Power (Conventional)	Power (Counter rotating)
30	0.175392	0.350784
40	0.233856	0.467712
50	0.29232	0.58464
60	0.350784	0.701568
70	0.409248	0.818496
80	0.467712	0.935424
90	0.526176	1.050032
120	0.701568	1.403136

Fig.1: - Voltage vs RPM

Fig.2:- Power vs RPM

CONCLUSION

This research investigated the potential to enhance wind energy conversion by implementing a counter-rotating vertical axis wind turbine (VAWT). By redesigning the generator to allow the rotor and stator to rotate in opposite directions, the system demonstrated a significant improvement in energy efficiency compared to traditional turbine models. The experimental data showed that the counter-rotating system consistently generated higher voltage and power outputs at various rotational speeds, with power output nearly doubling in certain cases. For example, at 120 RPM, the counter-rotating design produced 60.48 V and 1.403 W, compared to the conventional system's 30.24 V and 0.701 W.

Moreover, approximately 70% of the turbine's components were made from recycled materials, further promoting sustainability and cost-effectiveness. The Savonius VAWT, selected for its simplicity and high torque generation at low wind speeds, proved to be an effective option for areas with inconsistent wind patterns. The integration of components such as the Arduino Nano and Hall Effect sensor allowed for real-time performance monitoring and system optimization.

This study contributes to the development of renewable energy technologies by overcoming the efficiency limitations of conventional wind turbines. The counter-rotating VAWT design presents a promising solution for sustainable energy generation, especially in low-wind-speed regions. Future research could focus on scaling the design for industrial uses and optimizing the generator's performance under varying environmental conditions. Ultimately, this research highlights the potential of innovative engineering to

accelerate the shift toward cleaner and more efficient energy systems.

REFERENCES

1. Bayron, P., Kelso, R., & Chin, R. (2024). Experimental analysis of co-rotating and counter-rotating tandem horizontal-axis wind turbine performance and wake dynamics. *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics*, 253. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jweia.2024.105840>.
2. Chen, W. H., Ocreto, J. B., Wang, J. S., Hoang, A. T., Liou, J. H., Hwang, C. J., & Chong, W. T. (2021). Two-stage optimization of three and four straight-bladed vertical axis wind turbines (SB-VAWT) based on Taguchi approach. *E-Prime - Advances in Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Energy*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.prime.2021.100025>.
3. Hansen, J. T., Mahak, M., & Tzanakis, I. (2021). Numerical modelling and optimization of vertical axis wind turbine pairs: A scale up approach. *Renewable Energy*, 171, 1371–1381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2021.03.001>.
4. Javid, M. T., & Hassan, S. S. ul. (2024). Power performance optimization of twin vertical axis wind turbine for farm applications. *Wind Energy and Engineering Research*, 2, 100005. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.weer.2024.100005>.
5. Li, Y., Yang, S., Feng, F., & Tagawa, K. (2023). A review on numerical simulation based on CFD technology of aerodynamic characteristics of straight-bladed vertical axis wind turbines. In *Energy Reports* (Vol. 9, pp. 4360–4379). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2023.03.082>.

6. Mohamed, O. S., Melani, P. F., Balduzzi, F., Ferrara, G., & Bianchini, A. (2023). An insight on the physical mechanisms responsible of power augmentation in a pair of counter-rotating Darrieus turbines. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 284. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2023.116991>.
7. Nugraha, A. D., Garingging, R. A., Wiranata, A., Sitanggang, A. C., Supriyanto, E., Tanbar, F., & Muflikhun, M. A. (2025). Comparison of “Rose, Aero leaf, and Tulip” vertical axis wind turbines (VAWTs) and their characteristics for alternative electricity generation in urban and rural areas. *Results in Engineering*, 25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2024.103885>.
8. Peng, H. Y., Yang, X. R., Liu, H. J., & Sun, S. Y. (2024). Aerodynamic analysis of vertical axis wind turbines at various turbulent levels: Insights from 3D LES simulations. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobbe.2024.109899>.
9. Sahebzadeh, S., Rezaeiha, A., & Montazeri, H. (2022). Vertical-axis wind-turbine farm design: Impact of rotor setting and relative arrangement on aerodynamic performance of double rotor arrays. *Energy Reports*, 8, 5793–5819. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyr.2022.04.030>.
10. Seifi Davari, H., Botez, R. M., Seify Davari, M., Chowdhury, H., & Hosseinzadeh, H. (2024). Blade height impact on self-starting torque for Darrieus vertical axis wind turbines. *Energy Conversion and Management*: X, 24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecmx.2024.100814>.
11. Shouman, M. R., & Helal, M. M. (2023). Numerical investigation of improvement of counter rotating Savonius turbines performance with curtaining and fin addition on blade. *Alexandria Engineering Journal*, 75, 233–242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aej.2023.05.002>.
12. Somoano, M., & Huera-Huarte, F. J. (2022). Bio-inspired blades with local trailing edge flexibility increase the efficiency of vertical axis wind turbines. *Energy Reports*, 8, 3244–3250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyr.2022.02.151>.